

HYPERTENSIVE HEART DISEASE: RISK FACTORS, COMPLICATIONS, AND UNDERLYING MECHANISMS

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Abstract

Hypertensive heart disease encompasses both functional and structural dysfunctions in the left ventricle, left atrium, and coronary arteries, resulting from chronic uncontrolled hypertension. Despite its prevalence, hypertensive heart disease is often underreported, and the mechanisms contributing to its development and associated complications remain inadequately defined. In this review, we provide a comprehensive overview of the current understanding of hypertensive heart disease, focusing on the mechanisms involved in its progression and complications, particularly left ventricular hypertrophy, atrial fibrillation, heart failure, and coronary artery disease. Additionally, we highlight the roles of dietary salt, immune responses, and genetic predisposition in the pathogenesis of hypertensive heart disease.

Keywords: hypertensive heart disease, heart failure, hypertension, coronary artery disease, atrial fibrillation, immunity, salt

Introduction

Hypertensive heart disease refers to abnormalities in the heart's structure and function, particularly affecting the left ventricle, left atrium, and intramural coronary arteries, as a result of sustained elevated blood pressure. While the diagnostic criteria for hypertension differ between the American and European guidelines, most recommendations align, and the complications of chronic hypertension remain consistent. The criteria for defining hypertensive heart disease are not universally standardized. However, the European classification proposed by Gonzalez-Maqueda et al. from the Spanish Society of Cardiology uses the acronym "VIA" to describe the alterations: changes in the left ventricle (V), myocardial ischemia (I), and atrial fibrillation (A). Both European and American hypertension guidelines, as well as other international societies, agree that hypertensive heart disease encompasses left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), left atrial dilation, systolic and diastolic dysfunction, along with clinical symptoms such as arrhythmias, myocardial ischemia, and heart failure.

LVH is often one of the earliest indicators of hypertensive heart disease, initially acting as a compensatory mechanism to reduce ventricular wall stress. However, LVH can progress to more severe complications, including heart failure, arrhythmias, sudden cardiac arrest, ischemic stroke, end-stage renal disease (ESRD), and death.

Globally, the age-standardized prevalence of hypertension is approximately 32% in women and 34% in men. The prevalence of hypertension has been steadily rising, increasing by more than 138% between 1990 and 2019, now affecting 20 million individuals. Among people with hypertension, the prevalence of LVH is about 40%, with Black individuals tending to have higher left ventricular mass and more severe diastolic dysfunction compared to their White counterparts.

Risk Factors of Hypertensive Heart Disease

Hypertension is the primary risk factor for the development of hypertensive heart disease. Other contributing factors include older age, ethnicity, being overweight or obese, physical inactivity, excessive dietary salt intake, smoking, alcohol consumption, and comorbid conditions such as diabetes mellitus. These factors increase hemodynamic stress on the heart, and over time, the left ventricle undergoes hypertrophy to manage the increased workload. However, this compensatory hypertrophy eventually leads to heart failure.

Obesity is a particularly significant risk factor for hypertensive heart disease due to its role in increasing renin secretion, mediated by leptin production from adipose tissue, which elevates blood pressure and worsens existing hypertension. Additionally, obesity-induced increases in sympathetic nervous system activity disrupt the body's compensatory mechanisms, such as the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), further promoting cardiac fibrosis and endothelial dysfunction. This combination of factors accelerates the development and complications of hypertensive heart disease.

Beyond altering hemodynamics, obesity also contributes to hypertensive heart disease by triggering inflammation, lipid accumulation in tissues, and dysregulation of several intracellular signaling pathways. Obesity and hypertension often act synergistically through overlapping neurohormonal pathways, further exacerbating hypertensive heart disease and its associated complications, such as left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) and heart failure. Despite advancements in understanding these mechanisms, their complexity continues to challenge researchers.

Mechanisms of Hypertensive Heart Disease and Its Complications

Hypertensive heart disease often leads to a range of complications, including diastolic heart failure, systolic heart failure, or a combination of both. Individuals with hypertensive heart disease are at an increased risk for atrial fibrillation (AFib), perioperative ischemia, coronary artery disease, rehospitalization, kidney disease, heart valve diseases, aortic dissection, intramural hematoma, and aortic ulcer.

Left Ventricular Hypertrophy (LVH) Mechanisms in Hypertensive Heart Disease

LVH is an early compensatory response to the hemodynamic overload caused by chronic hypertension. It can predispose individuals with hypertension to cardiovascular events, even in asymptomatic cases with coronary artery calcifications, or in individuals with hypertension independent of treatment and other cardiovascular risk factors. Malignant LVH, characterized by elevated biomarkers of cardiac injury (e.g., NT-proBNP, high-sensitivity cardiac troponin T), is associated with severe outcomes such as heart failure with reduced ejection fraction, left ventricular dysfunction, and cardiovascular death. Biomarker levels can help identify patients at greater risk of adverse outcomes. It has also been observed that malignant LVH and related complications are more pronounced in Black individuals compared to White individuals. However, aggressive blood pressure control can prevent malignant LVH and reduce the risk of adverse events.

The pathogenesis of LVH differs by sex, with factors such as aortic impedance, systemic vascular resistance, and arterial compliance independently associated with wall thickness in women, making LVH more common and pronounced in women. LVH can manifest in two patterns: pathological or physiological. Pathological LVH involves increased extracellular connective tissue without proportional capillary growth, leading to myocardial fibrosis and diastolic dysfunction. In contrast, physiological LVH, such as that seen in response to physical

exercise, involves balanced myocyte hypertrophy and microvessel expansion without negative effects on left ventricular function.

Chronic hypertension leads to LVH through mechanisms such as gap junction lateralization, increased oxidative stress, abnormal calcium homeostasis, and overexpression of proteins like CD36 and matrix metalloproteinase-2 (MMP-2). These compensatory mechanisms help manage increased cardiac stress but can progress to decompensated heart failure if hypertension persists. LVH begins with myocyte hypertrophy, but prolonged elevated blood pressure can lead to cardiomyocyte death and dilated cardiomyopathy, marking the transition from compensated to decompensated heart failure. Structural changes in LVH may present as concentric or eccentric hypertrophy, depending on factors such as pressure load severity, genetic predisposition, and comorbidities.

The end result of LVH, if chronic hemodynamic stress continues, is progression to heart failure, either with preserved or reduced left ventricular ejection fraction. Evidence supports that LVH can regress with antihypertensive treatment, although variability in individual responses, including sex differences, has been reported. In some cases, LVH persists despite effective blood pressure control, reflecting the complexity of the condition.

Numerous proteins and mediators have been implicated in LVH development, including angiotensin II, endothelin-1, norepinephrine, and several kinases. Angiotensin II, the primary effector molecule of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), plays a critical role by inducing vasoconstriction, promoting sodium and water retention, and exerting pro-inflammatory and pro-fibrotic effects. These actions contribute to increased blood pressure and the structural remodeling seen in hypertensive heart disease.

Therapies for Left Ventricular Hypertrophy

Patients with left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) significantly benefit from intensive blood pressure lowering (to less than 120 mmHg) to prevent complications. Several therapies have demonstrated efficacy in reducing LVH and its associated risks in clinical trials. For instance, the neprilysin inhibitor sacubitril, in combination with the angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB) valsartan, has been shown to reduce left ventricular mass index more effectively than the ARB olmesartan in patients with hypertension. Another trial reported that the combination of the ARB telmisartan and simvastatin not only significantly lowered blood pressure but also reversed LVH and improved left ventricular systolic function. Similarly, a fixed-dose combination of perindopril, indapamide, and amlodipine (an ACE inhibitor, diuretic, and calcium channel blocker, respectively) demonstrated the ability to reverse LVH and improve outcomes in patients with essential hypertension over a 14-month period.

Additionally, a study by Lal et al. explored the use of allopurinol, a xanthine oxidase inhibitor typically used to lower plasma uric acid in gout patients, and found that high doses of allopurinol were more effective than febuxostat in reducing left ventricular mass and LVH. However, caution is necessary when using allopurinol in normouricemic individuals with controlled blood pressure, as it may increase oxidative stress.

Overall, the reversal of LVH appears to be more significant when both renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) inhibitors and sympathetic nervous system (SNS) inhibitors are used, rather than therapies that solely focus on blood pressure reduction. Other drugs and natural compounds have also been reported in clinical trials to mitigate the progression of LVH, including a nutraceutical combination of berberine, red yeast rice extract, and policosanol;

azelnidipine; losartan; low-dose eplerenone; metformin in patients with coronary artery disease without diabetes; and dietary interventions, such as low-fat and low-carbohydrate diets and regular consumption of green tea.

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